

Errors of measurement in scientometrics: Classification schemes and document types in citation and publication rankings

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Abstract

This research article delves into methodological challenges in scientometrics, focusing on errors stemming from the selection of classification schemes and document types. Employing two case studies, we examine the impact of these methodological choices on publication and citation rankings of institutions. We compute seven bibliometric indicators for over 8,434 institutions using 23 different classification schemes derived from Clarivate's InCites suite, as well as including all document types versus only citable items. Given the critical role university rankings play in research management and their methodological controversies, our goal is to propose a methodology that incorporates uncertainty levels when reporting bibliometric performance in professional practice. We then delve into differences in error estimates within research fields as well as between institutions from different geographic regions. The findings underscore the importance of responsible metric use in research evaluation, providing valuable insights for both bibliometricians and consumers of such data.

Keywords Responsible metrics; institutions rankings; citation indicators; publication counts; classifications of science; professional bibliometrics

Introduction

General Context

Errors constitute an inherent and inevitable aspect of the scientific process. Achieving perfect accuracy is unattainable, as tools for measurement will always include some level of uncertainty (Scuro 2004). According to the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology (BIPM et al. 2008), uncertainty is defined as a 'parameter associated with the result of a measurement, that characterizes the dispersion of the values that could reasonably be attributed to the measurand' (p. 2), where the measurand refers to the object being measured.

In the field of scientometrics, uncertainty and errors in measurement are usually overlooked. This is problematic for various reasons. First, neglecting uncertainty leads to the misuse of bibliometric indicators, which are then employed to legitimize decisions in conditions of limited trust or political controversy (Ràfols et al. 2016). The professionalization of bibliometrics in academic libraries (Gorraiz et al. 2020; Gumpfenberger et al. 2012) and Higher Education planning and research administration (Cox et al. 2019) has elevated bibliometric reporting to a valuable resource for decision-making. The widespread of metrics either explicitly or implicitly in research assessment exercises to support and judge individuals, departments or institutions (e.g., Hammarfelt and Rushforth 2017; Moed 2008) has created a landscape of tools and commercial solutions designed to respond to such demand. Bibliometric suites such as InCites

1 (from Clarivate) or Scival (Elsevier) offer a battery of research indicators based respectively on
2 bibliographic data from Web of Science and Scopus aimed at responding at this demand. These
3 indicators are not only built based on different sets of publications, but their definition also
4 differs leading sometimes to contradictory results for monitoring a common object (Robinson-
5 Garcia et al. 2020).

6
7 Second, bibliometric indicators are usually reported with high levels of precision, being the
8 more evident example the inclusion of up to three decimals of the Journal Impact Factor. This
9 is particularly worrying given the fact that even Garfield himself considered the impact factor
10 accurate only up to one decimal place (Bensman 2007). In later years he admitted that the only
11 reason ISI calculated the impact factors reported in the JCRs out to three decimal places was to
12 avoid the large number of ties that would have resulted in listing many journals alphabetically
13 in the impact factor rankings. Any analysis carried out under such a premise would de facto
14 lose their validity, and we should not forget that this error has a profound effect particularly at
15 the lower frequencies on ordinal rankings by the impact factor, on which most journal
16 evaluations are based (Schloegl and Gorraiz 2010).

17
18 This sense of false precision is also present in league tables and rankings in which variations in
19 positions may be the result of noise rather than improvement or decay, affecting the prestige of
20 those being portrayed in such tables (Bastedo and Bowman 2010; Gadd et al. 2021). While
21 there have been some efforts to recognize this uncertainty, such as the inclusion of stability
22 intervals in the Leiden Ranking and the introduction of position intervals in the Shanghai
23 Ranking below a certain threshold, these measures are, at best, modest. Among the many causes
24 for error or uncertainty in league tables we identify four types: 1) those derived from the
25 misassignment of research outputs (Waltman et al. 2012), 2) those derived from unequal
26 coverage of fields and locations in the database (Hicks 1999; Rafols et al. 2019; van Leeuwen
27 et al. 2001), 3) those inherent to the metadata such as incompleteness or low quality metadata
28 (Franceschini et al. 2015, 2016; Guerrero-Bote et al. 2021; Selivanova et al. 2019), and 4) those
29 derived from methodological choices. By the latter we refer to choices which can affect the
30 results without having *a priori* criteria set to justify such choices.

31 *Objectives of the study*

32 Our ultimate goal is to propose a methodological framework for evaluating measurements of
33 error and variability when reporting bibliometric indicators in professional practice. This is
34 particularly important if we aim to advocate and promote a responsible use of metrics in
35 research evaluation in times when their use are more questioned than ever (Torres-Salinas et al.
36 2023). Both, bibliometricians and producers of bibliometric data and indicators, have the
37 responsibility of bridging towards professionals and scientists (Leydesdorff et al. 2016)
38 consuming this data and promoting good practices on the use of such metrics.

39
40 In this paper we showcase an specific case study in which errors can be quantified, derived
41 from methodological choices. Specifically, we will focus on two case studies:

- 42
43 • **Diverging classification schemes.** Here errors arise from the selection of a given
44 classification scheme over another one when producing field normalized indicators
45 (Ruiz-Castillo and Waltman 2015). In this study we will focus on this latter aspect of
46 indicator variability by computing the same set of indicators on the same set of
47 publications using up to 23 different classification schemes. Differences are due to how
48 publications are categorized differently according to each classification. Also, they can
49 be due to the inclusion or exclusion of some of the records due to their unfitness

1 regarding the classification scheme (e.g., the Essential Science Indicators classification
2 scheme does not consider the fields of Arts and Humanities).

- 3 • **Selection of document types.** The second case study is derived from the definition and
4 selection of document types included in each analysis (Moed and Van Leeuwen 1995).
5 Here we will focus on estimating errors derived from including either all document
6 types in an analysis or only citable items.

7
8 In both cases we will be using publication and citation rankings of institutions as a means to
9 showcase how different indicators are affected by these errors and how it affects the positioning
10 of institutions in these rankings. It is important to emphasize that the indicators used in our
11 study, including those available through InCites, are part of a larger methodological framework
12 focused on evaluating measurement errors and variability. This framework aims to improve the
13 accuracy and reliability of bibliometric analyses, particularly when applied to institutional
14 rankings, which use in in research management is specially controversial (Gadd 2020).

15 *Structure of the paper*

16
17 The paper is structured as follows. Next, we review literature related to methodological
18 challenges imposed by the selection of classification schemes and definition of document types.
19 Then we define our methodological design for measuring errors in scientometrics. Here we
20 build on a previous study (Robinson-Garcia et al. 2023) to compute error estimates of 7
21 bibliometric indicators by using up to 23 different classification schemes. We use the InCites
22 bibliometric suite to calculate these indicators at the institutional level, analyzing a total of
23 8,433 institutions. Third, we report average relative error estimates when considering different
24 classification schemes at an aggregated level. We analyze differences in errors when accounting
25 for all document types versus when considering only citable documents (articles, reviews and
26 letters). Furthermore, we look into differences in errors when focusing on specific research
27 fields as well as on geographic regions. We conclude by reporting the implications our findings
28 have for professional practice and the use of scientometric indicators for decision-making.

29 **Literature review**

30 *Selection of field classifications of science*

31 The selection of an appropriate classification scheme is a matter of concern in the field of
32 scientometrics that has been discussed extensively in the literature using both quantitative and
33 qualitative data (Gómez et al. 1996; Janssens et al. 2009; Minguillo 2010; Perianes-Rodriguez
34 and Ruiz-Castillo 2018; Shu et al. 2019; Sugimoto and Weingart 2015). It is problematic for
35 various reasons. First, in relation to the level of analysis at which the field delineation is made.
36 Here, Gómez et al. (1996) point at four potential levels: document level, journal level, affiliation
37 level and author level. Determining the level at which field delineation is done is crucial in
38 terms of interpretability (Robinson-Garcia and Calero-Medina 2014) and accuracy (Shu et al.
39 2019) as there is a problem of attribution especially when embedded in evaluation practices
40 (Hansson et al. 2017). This issue is elegantly illustrated by Shu et al. (2019), who applied the
41 Chinese Library Classification system to a set of publications using two different levels of
42 analysis: at the journal level and the article level. They reported differences when rankings both:
43 institutions and authors in terms of productivity, although this influence was mitigated at the
44 institutional level.

45
46 Second, there are many classification systems available databases (Gusenbauer 2022), each data
47 sources has its own delineation of fields with *ad hoc* proposals (Gómez-Núñez et al. 2014;

1 Muñoz-Écija et al. 2019). But these classifications are not standardized, dealing to contradicting
2 and non-comparable results. This is an important point in bibliometric studies in order to allow
3 comparisons. The evaluation of the same content illustrates the structural differences in the
4 databases, which is informative for interpreting bibliometric analyses (Stahlschmidt and
5 Stephen 2022). A comparative study between the subject categories classification system in
6 Web of Science and the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) in Scopus, indicated that
7 both classification were “too lenient in assigning journals to categories” (Wang and Waltman
8 2016, p. 359). That is, they tended to include journals in multiple categories regardless how
9 well connected they were in terms of citations with such categories. Another example is the
10 classification proposed by Thijs et al. (2015), which combined hierarchical clustering and
11 bibliographic coupling to create a 24 field classification system. This classification seemed to
12 deviate greatly from the 22 fields from Essential Science Indicators included in Web of Science.
13 These irregularities and discrepancies can lead to inconsistent outcomes (Reuven and Rosenfeld
14 2022) hindering the interpretation of bibliometric indicators. As a means to improve these
15 classification systems, some authors have suggested the use of hybrid methods, that is, refine
16 journal-level classifications with paper level citation clustering and text mining to improve
17 these classifications (e.g., Janssens et al. 2009).

18
19 Third, there is the issue of balancing between accuracy, granularity and interpretability (Börner
20 et al. 2012). In this sense, there are many multi-level classification systems which try to offer
21 combinations by which users can zoom in or panning out. For instance, the publication level
22 classification implemented by the CWTS (Waltman and van Eck 2012) is a three-tier
23 classification system which goes spans from broad areas to micro topics based on direct citation
24 networks between papers. Another example is the Australian and New Zealand Standard
25 Research Classification (Australian Bureau of Statistics 2008) used by Dimensions, which also
26 includes a three-level hierarchical classification system. The level of granularity of a
27 classification will depend on the purpose for which the classification system is used. While
28 broad fields may be desirable when reporting findings, more accuracy can lead to more robust
29 indicators when normalizing by field (Ruiz-Castillo and Waltman 2015). In this sense, it is
30 important to note that different indicators will show different levels of variability when moving
31 from one classification system to another (Perianes-Rodriguez and Ruiz-Castillo 2018).

32 33 *Definition of document types*

34
35 The definition and inclusion of document types will have a vital influence on the outcome of a
36 bibliometric report. Furthermore, their definition and typology will vary depending on the
37 database used as a data source. The underlying principle behind this distinction of documents
38 is that different types of documents serve different functions in the scientific system and hence
39 are read and cited differently, leading to differences in citation distributions (Lundberg 2007;
40 Moed and Van Leeuwen 1995). Here we observe inconsistencies between databases, finding
41 that a paper categorized as ‘Article’ in Web of Science (WoS) might be defined as a ‘Review’
42 in Scopus, while Dimensions makes no distinction whatsoever (Visser et al. 2021).

43
44 Scientometric studies have historically distinguished between citable and non-citable items
45 (Heneberg 2014). But databases often misclassify records, being letters and reviews the most
46 affected by these inaccuracies (Donner 2017). Gorraiz and Schloegl (2008) reported that there
47 was a difference of over 10% between the sum of articles and reviews reported in Web of
48 Science and Scopus. On a different study, Haunschild and Bornmann (2022) compared the
49 scores that result from different normalization procedures, which have been performed based

1 on three different approaches of handling the document types. At least two of these approaches
 2 are in use in popular university rankings. They showed that field-normalized scores strongly
 3 depend on the choice of different document types and that the results on the aggregated level
 4 (country, institution) are not supported by results on the level of individual publications.
 5

6 **Data and methods**

7 *Data collection*

8 Data was retrieved using the bibliometric suite InCites, which includes the Web of Science
 9 Core Collection including the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI), for the period 1980-
 10 2022. In this study we worked at the institutional level, using their “Organizations” option, that
 11 is, their disambiguated list of institutions (more on issues for disambiguating institutional names
 12 in Waltman et al. 2012). We include a total of 8,434 institutions which have published at least
 13 1,000 documents (all document types) in the study period. InCites provides for each unit under
 14 analysis a battery of bibliometric indicators which can be computed according to some
 15 customizable parameters. One of them being the election of a given classification system. We
 16 select 23 of the classification schemes currently available in InCites, including in here multi-
 17 level classification systems. Table 1 provides a description of each of them, indicating the
 18 number of categories per level and the assignment method Web of Science uses to create such
 19 tables. Except of the Citation Topics classification, which follow the methodology developed
 20 by Waltman and van Eck (2012), all schemes follow either a journal based method or aggregate
 21 Web of Science subject categories (which also are journal based).
 22

23 **Table 1. Description of the 23 classification schemes employed for the analysis***

Acronym	Denomination	Description	Levels and categories	Method
ANVUR	ANVUR Category Schema	Official academic fields and disciplines list for Italian Universities Research and Teaching.	(1) 17 broad categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
FOR	Australia ERA FOR	Revised Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC 2020)	(1) 24 FoR2 (2) 212 FoR4	Journal mapping
CAPEB	CAPEB Brazil	Classification created by the Foundation CAPEB, linked to the Ministry of Education (Brazil)	(1) Capes 9 (2) Capes 49 (3) Capes 121	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
CHINA	China SCADC Subject Categories	State Council Academic Degree Committee (SCADC) and Ministry of Education of China	(1) Broader 13 (2) Granular 96	Journal and other sources mapping
SHANGHAI	Shanghai Ranking Global Ranking of Subjects	Rankings of universities in 54 subjects across, Natural, Life, Medical, and Social Sciences...	(1) 54 academic subjects	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
TOPICS	Citation Topics	Algorithmically derived citation clusters (using an algorithm developed by CWTS, Leiden)	(1) Macro 10 (2) Meso 326	algorithmically on citation relationships
ESI	Essential Science Indicators Research Areas	All documents from Science Citation Index Expanded and Social Science Citation Index	(1) 22 broad categories	Journal mapping
FAPESP	FAPESP Brazil	Created by the São Paulo Research Foundation	(1) 9 High Level (2) 72 Detailed categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
GIIP	Institutional Profiles Research Areas	Clarivate Analytics has been profiling the world’s leading universities and research institutions	(1) 6 broad academic fields	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
KAKEN	KAKEN Category Schema (10 and 66)	From Japan called the Kakenhi Program (Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research).	(1) 10 L2 (2) 66 L3	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
OECD	OECD Category Schema	Revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) Classification of the Frascati Manual.	(1) 42 fields	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
PL19	PL19 Category Schema	The Polish PL19 category schema is used for annual evaluation exercise	(1) 44 underlying categories	Journal mapping
RIS	Research and Innovation Strategies for Specialization	The Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialization (RIS3) for Latvia	(1) 7 specialization fields	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
UKREF14	UK RAE Units of Assessment 2018	UK 2014 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) Units of Assessment (UoA)	(1) 36 categories	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)

UKREF21	UK REF Units of Assessment 2021	UK 2021 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) Units of Assessment (UoA)	(1) 36 units of assessment	Category-to-category mapping (WoS)
WOS	Web of Science Research Areas	The Web of Science schema comprises approximately 250 subject areas	(1) 250	---

* Information extracted from <https://incites.help.clarivate.com/Content/Research-Areas/research-areas.htm> The data presented reproduce higher levels of categorization. Specifically, certain categories (FOR, CAPES, CHINA, TOPICS, FAPESP, KAKEN) encompass multiple levels, which are not detailed in this table. The total of 16 listed categories, when including the sublevels of the mentioned categories, sums up to the 23 classification schemes analysed in this paper.

1
2 For each institution we focused on seven different indicators: total number of publications,
3 times cited, the Category Normalized Citation Indicator, top 1% most cited papers, top 10%
4 most cited papers, average percentile, and H-Index. Each indicator is computed 46 times;
5 according to the 23 different classification schemes and including all document types versus
6 only citable items.

7 *Calculation of errors*

8 The calculation of the errors followed the standard definition used in the experimental sciences,
9 where the absolute error of a measurement is the difference between the measured value and
10 the true value. In cases where the true value is unknown, it is replaced with the mean value
11 obtained after multiple iterations of the measurement. In our case, each indicator is calculated
12 a total of 23 times for each classification scheme and twice when looking into document types.
13

14 To accurately determine the absolute error for each institution, we first calculate the mean value
15 of the repeated measurements of each indicator. The absolute error for a given institution, Δx_i
16 is then computed as the difference between its measured value and the reference mean value.
17 Mathematically, the absolute error of an institution can be defined as:

$$18 \Delta x_{\text{mean}} = (\text{ABS}(\Delta x_1) + \text{ABS}(\Delta x_2) + \dots + \text{ABS}(\Delta x_n))/n$$

19
20
21 Where x_i corresponds to an institution and $\text{ABS}(\Delta x_i)$ is its absolute error.
22

23 Let's consider we want to compute the absolute error after retrieving the number of publications
24 produced by three departments from three different bibliometric databases. The measurements
25 obtained for from each database are shown in Table 2.
26

27 **Table 2. Mock up example of number of publications obtained for three institutions from three**
28 **different databases**

	Database I	Database II	Database III
Department A	250	260	240
Department B	300	310	290
Department C	280	270	290

29
30 For each research department, we first calculate the mean number of publications across the
31 three databases:
32

- 33 • Department A: 250
- 34 • Department B: 300
- 35 • Department C: 280

36
37 Next, we calculate the absolute error for each database by comparing the measured values with
38 the mean value for each department and dividing by the number of measurements. Hence, the
39 absolute error for Department A would be:

$$\Delta x_{\text{mean}} = \frac{|250 - 250| + |260 - 250| + |240 - 250|}{3} = 6.67$$

Following the calculation of absolute errors, we also compute relative and percentage errors, facilitating comparisons between indicators across different classification schemes. The relative error is obtained by dividing the absolute error by the mean value, while the percentage error is calculated by multiplying the relative error by 100. Following the example of Department A, we now show its relative and percentage errors:

$$\text{Relative Error} = \frac{6.67}{250} \approx 0.0267$$

$$\text{Percentage Error} = 0.0267 \times 100 \approx 2.67\%$$

To account for the variability observed in repeated measurements, we calculated the confidence intervals associated with each error measurement. These intervals were derived from the standard deviation of the repeated measurements and provide a range within which the true value is expected to lie with a specified level of confidence.

Results

General overview of error estimates by classification scheme and document types

In table 3 we include an overview of our final dataset. For each classification scheme we include the total number of institutions covered when considering all document types and when considering only citable documents. As observed, only the WOS classification includes the 8,434 institutions originally included in our dataset when considering all document types. Simply by filtering to citable documents, we lose up to 559 institutions in the best of cases (WOS). The classification scheme with the lowest coverage is FOR1 which includes 42% of the institutions and 18% of documents, a share that increases up to 20% when considering only citable documents.

Table 3. Total institutions and publications per classification scheme and document types

Classification scheme	Institutions		Records	
	All docs.	Citable only	All docs.	Citable only
WOS	8,434	7,875	63,908,002	51,399,082
KAKENL2	8,433	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
KAKENL3	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
UKREF21	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
RIS	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
OCDE	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
GIPP	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
FAPESP	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
CAPES9	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
CAPES49	8,432	7,874	63,895,799	51,389,373
ANVUR	8,431	7,874	63,888,303	51,389,373
UKREF14	8,414	7,865	63,671,768	51,241,279
CAPES121	8,380	7,837	63,011,376	50,799,943

SHANGHAI	8,231	7,737	59,830,551	48,881,578
CHINA BROAD	8,141	7,610	58,977,093	47,077,808
CHINA NARROW	8,141	7,610	58,977,087	47,077,802
TOPICSMACRO	7,931	7,717	53,728,425	49,126,966
TOPICSMESO	7,931	7,717	53,728,425	49,126,966
TOPICSMICRO	7,931	7,717	53,728,425	49,126,966
PL19	7,746	7,187	51,317,825	40,102,542
ESI	7,497	6,943	49,844,239	39,158,270
FOR2	6,560	5,959	36,711,808	27,927,846
FOR1	3,549	3,348	11,671,816	10,107,716

1 Next, we report the average estimated error for each classification resulting from considering
2 either all document types or only citable documents (Table 4). As observed, the lowest relative
3 error is reported for the H-Index and the total number of citations, in both case below 1% for
4 all classification schemes. We observe error estimates ranging between 0.7 for the CNCI to
5 5.3% for the average percentile indicators. On the other extreme we find that number of
6 documents is the indicator with the largest estimated error (7.4% on average). Furthermore, we
7 observe different levels of variability in the error by indicator. While in the cases of times cited
8 and H-Index these are below 0.1%, in the case of top 1% highly cited papers, we observe a
9 variability of 8.3 between the largest estimated error (11% for TOPICSMICRO) and the lowest
10 value (2.7% for TOPICSMACRO). A similar case we observe again in the number of
11 publications, where there is a variability of up to 6.1% between FOR2 (9.6%) and the three
12 TOPICS schemes (3.5%).

13

14

Table 4. Average relative error by classification scheme considering document type

Classification scheme	Docs	+/-	Times Cited	+/-	CNCI	+/-	Top 1%	+/-	Top 10%	+/-	Avg. percentile	+/-	H-Index	+/-
WOS	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.2	2.0	4.5	3.7	2.7	2.3	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
KAKENL2	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	3.0	4.9	4.1	2.7	2.3	4.2	3.6	0.3	0.3
KAKENL3	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.8	2.7	4.5	3.8	2.7	2.3	4.2	3.6	0.3	0.3
UKREF21	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.7	2.6	4.7	3.9	2.9	2.4	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
RIS	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.3	3.2	5.0	4.3	2.7	2.2	4.2	3.6	0.3	0.3
OCDE	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.8	2.7	4.8	4.0	2.9	2.4	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
GIPP	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.9	5.0	4.2	2.9	2.3	4.4	3.7	0.3	0.3
FAPESP	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.9	2.8	4.8	3.9	2.8	2.4	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
CAPES9	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.9	5.1	4.3	2.9	2.4	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
CAPES49	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.7	2.6	4.6	3.9	2.7	2.3	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
ANWUR	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.9	4.8	4.0	2.9	2.5	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
UKREF14	8.0	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.6	4.6	3.9	2.9	2.4	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
CAPES121	7.9	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.1	4.5	3.7	2.7	2.3	4.3	3.6	0.3	0.3
SHANGHAI	7.7	6.0	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.5	4.5	3.8	2.7	2.2	3.9	3.3	0.3	0.3
CHINA BROAD	8.2	6.3	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.9	4.9	4.2	2.9	2.4	4.4	3.7	0.3	0.3
CHINA NARROW	8.2	6.3	0.8	0.6	2.7	2.6	4.6	3.7	3.1	2.6	4.5	3.7	0.3	0.3
TOPICSMACRO	3.5	2.6	0.8	0.6	1.0	0.9	2.7	2.4	1.3	1.0	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.3
TOPICSMESO	3.5	2.6	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.7	4.3	3.5	1.2	1.0	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.3
TOPICSMICRO	3.5	2.6	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.6	11.0	6.2	1.6	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.3
PL19	8.6	6.6	0.8	0.6	3.4	3.4	5.1	4.3	2.8	2.3	4.6	3.8	0.3	0.3

ESI	8.7	6.5	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.8	4.8	4.0	3.0	2.4	4.5	3.7	0.3	0.3
FOR2	9.6	7.0	0.8	0.6	2.8	2.7	4.8	3.9	2.8	2.2	5.3	4.0	0.3	0.3
FOR1	4.7	3.4	0.8	0.6	1.6	1.4	3.5	2.8	1.7	1.3	2.0	1.7	0.3	0.3

1
2 Given differences on the institutional coverage observed in Table 3, we present error estimates
3 only considering institutions which are present in all schemes. To show how the exclusion of
4 schemes with lower coverage affect error estimates, we present the world average relative error
5 when considering the 23 classification schemes and considering only the top 13 with the largest
6 institutional coverage (Table 5). Here we observe relatively small differences between focusing
7 on all document types or citable documents. When considering the 23 classification schemes,
8 we observe that the largest estimated errors are found for number of documents (12.2-12.8%)
9 and top 1% most highly cited papers (10.0-11.2%). When reducing the number of
10 classifications, we find how the error estimates are reduced drastically for size dependent
11 indicators (docs, times cited and H-Index) while they are very similar for non-size dependent
12 indicators (CNCI, Top 1%, Top 10% and avg. percentile). However, while in the case of the
13 CNCI and the average percentile, the error is reduced for 13 classification schemes, it increases
14 for the Top 1% and Top 10% indicators.

15 **Table 5. World Percentage errors considering 23 and 13 classification schemes by document**
16 **type selection**

17

Indicators	23 schemes		13 schemes	
	All docs	Citable only	All docs	Citable only
Docs	12.8	12.2	0.2	0.2
+/-	1.9	1.9	0.2	0.2
Times Cited	9.2	9.2	0.2	0.2
+/-	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2
CNCI	4.8	4.6	3.6	3.4
+/-	1.7	1.4	1.8	1.5
Top 1%	11.2	10.0	10.0	11.8
+/-	4.1	3.9	4.8	6.6
Top 10%	5.8	5.8	5.3	6.0
+/-	1.8	1.7	1.8	2.2
Avg. Percentile	3.1	2.4	2.2	2.3
+/-	1.1	0.7	0.7	0.7
H-Index	4.1	4.1	0.1	0.1
+/-	0.4	0.4	0.1	0.1

18 *Field differences in error estimates for document types: Macro Topic and ESI fields*

19 As a means to deepen on how the choice of including all document types or only those defined
20 as citable, in tables 6 and 7 we look into differences in error estimates by field. To do so, we
21 use TOPICSMACRO scheme formed by 10 major fields and the 22 ESI fields respectively.

22

23 In the case of the macro topics, we observe that the largest errors can be found in the fields of
24 Arts & Humanities (between 0.6% for H-Index and 8.1% for number of documents), followed
25 by Clinical & Life Sciences (between 0.4% for the H-Index and 6.0% for number of
26 documents). Interestingly, the greatest variability in percentage error is found in the number of
27 documents, for which Arts & Humanities is the field with the largest average error estimate,

1 while Electrical Engineering, Electronics & Computer Science has an average percentage error
 2 of 1%. The rest of the patterns between indicators hold to what we observed in Table 4.

3
 4 By using the citation topics, we considered that their calculation is only possible for
 5 publications with cited references. Therefore, all the document types usually non-including
 6 cited references (like e.g., meeting abstracts) are automatically excluded. That is the reason why
 7 the differences between using all document types and only citable items will be lower than
 8 expected when considering other classifications elaborated on journal level.

9
 10 **Table 6. Percentage errors from document type selection by Macro Topics**

TOPICSMACRO	Docs	+/-	Times Cited	+/-	CNCI	+/-	Top 1%	+/-	Top 10%	+/-	Avg. percentile	+/-	H-Index	+/-
Agriculture, Environment & Ecology	2.3	1.1	1.0	0.5	0.7	0.5	2.1	1.7	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.297	0.3
Arts & Humanities	8.1	2.2	3.0	0.8	1.7	1.0	5.2	3.8	2.5	1.2	2.8	1.0	0.6	0.7
Chemistry	1.9	1.1	1.0	0.6	0.5	0.4	1.8	1.7	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3
Clinical & Life Sciences	6.0	2.8	1.4	0.6	1.6	1.3	3.5	2.7	1.7	1.2	1.0	0.6	0.4	0.3
Earth Sciences	2.3	1.0	0.7	0.3	0.6	0.4	1.8	1.4	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2
Electrical Engineering, Electronics & Computer Science	1.0	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.3	1.2	1.2	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3
Engineering & Materials Science	1.0	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.3	1.6	1.5	0.6	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
Mathematics	1.3	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.4	1.6	1.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4
Physics	1.4	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.3	1.3	1.1	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Social Sciences	3.4	1.6	1.3	0.6	1.0	0.8	2.4	1.9	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.4

11
 12 In the case of the ESI fields (Table 7) a different pattern is observed. Here it is the
 13 Multidisciplinary category the one accounting for the largest errors in all indicators with notable
 14 differences with respect to the rest of the categories. The exception is found in the average
 15 percentile with other fields exhibit greater percentage errors (e.g., Clinical Medicine, Social
 16 Sciences, general). The other exhibiting a large, estimated error is Clinical Medicine, where the
 17 error in terms of number of documents is just above 20%.

18 **Table 7. Percentage errors from document type selection by ESI fields**

ESI	Docs	+/-	Times Cited	+/-	CNCI	+/-	Top 1%	+/-	Top 10%	+/-	Avg. percentile	+/-	H-Index	+/-
Agricultural Sciences	3.5	2.7	0.4	0.3	1.8	1.5	3.0	2.3	1.3	1.0	1.8	1.7	0.1	0.2
Biology & Biochemistry	11.5	5.5	1.3	0.610	3.0	2.2	6.5	4.7	3.9	2.9	6.9	3.8	0.4	0.3
Chemistry	5.4	4.6	0.7	0.6	3.2	3.1	5.5	5.4	3.3	3.6	3.8	4.0	0.2	0.3
Clinical Medicine	20.5	5.5	1.8	0.6	6.5	4.6	8.0	4.7	6.5	3.5	10.6	3.2	0.4	0.3
Computer Science	3.1	1.2	0.8	0.5	1.4	1.1	3.0	2.2	1.1	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.3	0.3
Economics & Business	6.6	2.9	1.2	0.5	3.0	2.3	4.8	3.7	1.8	1.1	3.5	2.0	0.4	0.3
Engineering	1.9	1.1	0.5	0.3	1.7	1.5	2.9	2.6	1.3	1.0	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.2
Environment/Ecology	2.2	0.9	1.1	0.5	1.1	0.7	2.1	1.5	1.0	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.4
Geosciences	3.5	1.4	0.7	0.3	1.2	0.9	3.2	2.8	1.1	0.9	1.1	0.7	0.2	0.3
Immunology	13.7	3.1	1.8	0.5	3.1	2.1	5.5	3.4	4.6	2.3	6.9	2.2	0.5	0.3
Materials Science	1.1	0.6	0.3	0.2	1.1	1.0	2.3	2.4	0.8	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1
Mathematics	1.3	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.5	1.9	1.6	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.2
Microbiology	4.1	1.3	1.5	0.7	1.1	0.8	3.1	2.3	1.3	0.8	1.2	0.7	0.4	0.3

Molecular Biology & Genetics	9.1	2.8	0.9	0.3	2.8	1.7	5.0	2.4	3.9	1.8	5.3	1.9	0.3	0.2
Multidisciplinary	23.0	22.6	3.1	1.9	12.6	7.0	19.9	15.1	13.1	9.4	8.8	9.8	1.1	0.8
Neuroscience & Behavior	14.6	3.8	1.2	0.4	3.4	2.5	5.4	3.3	3.6	3.0	8.4	2.4	0.2	0.2
Pharmacology & Toxicology	11.8	4.5	1.6	0.7	2.8	2.0	5.2	3.5	4.1	2.4	6.4	2.8	0.4	0.4
Physics	1.6	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.6	0.4	1.5	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2
Plant & Animal Sciences	5.2	2.8	1.0	0.4	2.0	1.4	4.2	3.4	2.0	1.6	2.2	1.8	0.2	0.3
Psychiatry/Psychology	12.5	2.8	1.3	0.5	3.3	2.4	4.8	3.2	3.4	1.7	7.5	1.9	0.3	0.3
Social Sciences, general	15.1	5.6	1.5	0.5	4.1	3.0	5.8	3.9	4.1	2.4	9.8	4.6	0.4	0.3
Space Science	1.3	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.5	0.4	1.2	1.0	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1

1
2 *Regional differences in error estimates for classification schemes: United States vs. South*
3 *America*

4 Finally, we delve into regional differences in order to understand how homogeneous or
5 heterogeneous is the effect of using different classification schemes in institutions located in
6 different parts of the world. As an illustrative example, in Table 8 we report the average
7 percentage errors of institutions located in the United States and in South America. Again, we
8 report errors considering all document types or citable documents, as well as including the 23
9 classification schemes or only the 13 classifications with the largest institutional coverage.
10 While the general pattern of errors is similar to that observed in table 5, we do observe
11 differences between institutions of these two regions. Overall, we observe that differences of
12 error are always lower than 1% with some exceptions. The largest difference is that observed
13 for the Top 1% most highly cited publications, where differences of error are above 4%
14 (favoring US institutions) when considering the 23 classification schemes. These differences
15 are below 1% when considering only 13 schemes. The other exception is for all document types
16 and Top 10%, where the difference of error is just above 1%, being larger for South American
17 institutions.
18

19 **Table 8. Percentage errors from classification schemes for institutions located in the United**
20 **States vs. institutions located in South America**

Indicators	UNITED STATES				SOUTH AMERICA			
	23 schemes		13 schemes		23 schemes		13 schemes	
	All docs	Citable only	All docs	Citable only	All docs	Citable only	All docs	Citable only
Docs	13.8	11.8	0.2	0.3	12.4	12.6	0.1	0.1
+/-	1.6	1.5	0.2	0.2	1.0	1.3	0.1	0.1
Times Cited	9.3	9.3	0.3	0.3	9.3	9.2	0.2	0.2
+/-	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1
CNCI	5.4	4.9	4.5	3.6	5.1	5.0	2.0	2.0
+/-	1.9	1.4	2.3	1.6	1.2	1.4	0.8	0.6
Top 1%	8.6	7.6	9.2	8.8	13.2	12.2	9.3	9.7
+/-	2.7	2.4	4.3	4.1	3.6	3.4	3.8	4.1
Top 10%	5.0	5.2	5.1	5.2	6.0	6.0	5.0	5.3
+/-	1.2	1.3	1.9	1.8	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5
Avg. Percentile	4.1	2.0	1.9	2.0	3.2	2.9	2.4	2.5
+/-	1.1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.8	0.6	0.5	0.5

H-Index	4.3	4.3	0.1	0.1	4.0	4.0	0.1	0.1
+/-	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1

1

2 **Conclusions & Discussion**

3 In bibliometric practices as well as in many bibliometric studies, several choices always have
4 to be made which naturally can seriously affect the results obtained and their interpretations.
5 In this article, we have assessed the magnitude of these errors occurring in two recurring
6 situations: 1) considering the document type and 2) considering different classification
7 schemes. Moreover, we think that a science that is mainly based on statistics should indicate
8 the validity of the retrieved values, both of its numbers and of its decimals, in order to reveal
9 their significance. The purpose of this paper is to reveal bibliometricians which errors will be
10 derived from their document type and classification schemes decisions.

11

12 In the first case, we have seen how the choice of what type of documents should be included in
13 the analysis, can influence not only the indicators of publication activity, where they are
14 manifest, but also those of impact and especially those of normalized impact, such as the CNCI,
15 and the Top 1% and Top 10%, which are the most commonly used in bibliometric practices
16 (Moed 2017).

17

18 Generally, in this case, the decision falls between choosing the “citable publications” or all
19 types of documents that are available. This difference was already introduced by Garfield, when
20 he introduced his measure of the Journal Impact Factor by considering only the citable items
21 (articles, reviews and proceedings) in the denominator, while in the numerator including the
22 citations to all document types.

23

24 Our study shows that this decision can severely distort the results in the Essential Science
25 Indicators (ESI) Category “Multidisciplinary”. As it is well known, this category appears as
26 well in the ESI classification scheme as in the Journal Citation Reports, while in InCites all
27 these publications are reallocated to categories that are more precise. Anyhow, our results show
28 the big differences bibliometricians may confront with dealing with journals and journal impact
29 measures assigned to this category.

30

31 Other categories are also affected by the document type decision, especially *Clinical Medicine*,
32 *Immunology* and *Pharmacology & Toxicology*, where percentage errors higher than 4% are
33 reported for the calculation of the top 10% most cited, that is commonly used as a measure for
34 academic excellence. These are mainly due to the effect of the *Meeting Abstracts*, as it has
35 already been often reported (Gorraiz et al. 2016). This also corroborated by the results obtained
36 when using the Citation Topics – Macrotopics. In this case, the percentage errors are
37 considerably diminished, because Meeting Abstracts lack of references and cannot be
38 considered in this scheme. *Editorial Materials* and *Book Chapters* are the other document types
39 responsible for the differences in the impact measures, also in other categories like *Social*
40 *Sciences, general, Biology & Biochemistry* and *Psychiatry/Psychology*. Interestingly, *Physics*,
41 *Space Physics* and *Mathematics* are almost not affected, and the only consideration of citable
42 items is a sound decision.

43

44 Therefore, in our analyses we are considering errors due to three different decision-making
45 processes: 1) to select a classification scheme, 2) to select a classification schema based on
46 journal level versus one based on document level; and 3) to use a classification schema on
47 different aggregation levels. And for the bibliometrician community it is crucial to be able to

1 estimate the effect that these decisions are expected to have on the values calculated for their
2 impact measures.

3
4 In this our first error analysis study, we have considered all the classification schemes available
5 nowadays in InCites and calculated the errors due to their selection. In a first instance, we
6 wanted to extend our work to the classifications available in SciVal and compare our results.
7 But to our great surprise, we discovered that the selection of the classification did not change
8 the impact results at the working aggregation level (meso-level) in that analytical tool, so they
9 could not be incorporated into our study.

10
11 Our results show the alterations that the impact measures would undergo in the case of using
12 another classification scheme. Of the four normalized impact indicators, the top 1% shows the
13 largest margin of error ranging from 3 to 17%. This is mainly due to the short number of
14 publications contributing to this percentile. The measure of excellence (Top 10% most cited)
15 fluctuates between 5 and 8%, and the average percentile varying between approximately 1.5
16 and 3%. The value of the CNCI can vary from 1.5 to 5%.

17
18 Differences in the values of the H-index are only reported when including classification
19 schemes reducing considerably the number of publications considered (10 from 23 Schemes).
20 Furthermore, topological factors, would only increase slightly these errors or deviations due to
21 the selection of a classification scheme. In a study case, the differences between North-
22 American and South-American institutions, the discrepancies between the percentage errors
23 were only slightly higher for the percentile indicators for the South-American organizations
24 when considering only the citable items. Finally, our results show that the decision made by for
25 using all types of documents or only the citable ones hardly alter the divergences resulting from
26 the use of one or the other classification system (see table 5) at the meso level.

27 **Limitations and further research**

28
29
30 All the analyses in this study have been carried out at the meso-level, which is the most
31 significant for this purpose. All analyses have been performed for the period 1980-2022 to
32 increase the significance of the results. For shorter periods, the errors, especially for indicators
33 that are not standardized, such as the number of publications and the number of citations, would
34 naturally be much higher and should therefore be recalculated for each specific situation in
35 further studies

36
37 At the macro level very similar results are expected, while at the micro level, i.e., in the
38 evaluation of individuals, the analysis is much more problematic due to the small number of
39 publications available, and the great diversity of the cases and criteria to be considered (such as
40 gender, age of career, etc.). For example, Åström, Hammarfelt and Hansson (2017) discuss how
41 scientific publications can be categorized in different fields depending on the unit of assessment
42 being evaluated: the publication, the individual or the institution. They found variations in terms
43 of purpose of categorization as well as purpose of evaluation, i.e., the definition and function
44 of the publications depending on whether it is situated in a context of scholarly communication
45 or a context of research evaluation. The raising questions such as on what levels the distinctions
46 are made, and in terms of on what principles the categories are being defined. The varying
47 functions of the boundary object becomes critical when contextualized within the concept of
48 infrastructures (publication databases, citation indices, evaluation systems and classification
49 systems). Therefore, it is always advisable to perform the measurements on a case-by-case basis
50 and with different data sources and purpose of use.

1
2 One of the most subtle and critical problems of bibliometrics is classifications. As is well
3 known, there is no standard, and each database and even each nation or continent uses its own
4 schema for their evaluation systems. That is why Clarivate, in a big effort, tried to collect the
5 most used ones on different aggregation levels (macro, meso and micro) in its flagship product
6 “InCites” and to use them for the calculation of the most common bibliometric indicators (see
7 Table 1). Besides, classification systems are usually created at the level of journals (Pudovkin
8 & Garfield, 2002) but also at the paper level (Waltman & van Eck 2012; Rivest et al 2021).
9 Comparisons of these two levels of aggregations, journal classification versus paper
10 classification using the same classification scheme and the same dataset revealed that almost
11 half of the papers could be misclassified in journal classification systems (Shu et al 2019). When
12 comparing rankings of the most productive institutions and authors, classification of papers has
13 less influence on rankings at the institutional level than at the individual level (Shu et al 2020),
14 which has implications for bibliometric evaluation. At this point, it is important to emphasize
15 that InCites also includes other classifications based not only on journal level (e.g. ESI and
16 WoS subject categorization) but also most recent ones based on document level like the
17 classification system builds on “Citation Topics”, algorithmically derived citation clusters using
18 an algorithm developed by CWTS, Leiden¹. Further studies can bring light on differences using
19 journal or article level when calculating errors.

20
21 Another limitation of this study is that we have performed all the analyses on a single data
22 source, the Web of Science Core Collection. Therefore, it will be necessary to perform future
23 analyses comparing the results in different sources, such as WoS CC, Scopus, Dimensions and
24 even other Open sources, such as OpenAlex, Crossref or Lens. We are fully convinced that
25 these studies will be of great help to all those involved in providing bibliometric services to be
26 able to argue, justify and foresee the effects of the decisions they have had to make in carrying
27 out their analyses.

28
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